

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

№ 2(11)

27.02.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

SJIF 2024

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Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
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THE FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION IMPACTS ON THE ECONOMY

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Annotation. *The scientific article is devoted to the study of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and its impact on modern society and economy. The article analyzes the main technological innovations characteristic of this revolution, such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of things, industrial automation and cyber-physical systems. The advantages and challenges that accompany the introduction of these technologies in various sectors of the economy are considered.*

Keywords: *Digital transformation, artificial intelligence, digital economy, fourth, industrial revolution, technology, economics, information technology, social and environmental aspects, policy and regulation, digital infrastructure, globalization, blockchain technology, labor market and employment, automation.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ ЧЕТВЕРТОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ РЕВОЛЮЦИИ НА ЭКОНОМИКУ

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Аннотация. *Научная статья посвящена исследованию Четвертой промышленной революции и ее влиянию на современное общество и экономику. В статье анализируются основные технологические инновации, характерные для этой революции, такие как искусственный интеллект, Интернет вещей, промышленная автоматизация и киберфизические системы. Рассмотрены преимущества и проблемы, сопровождающие внедрение этих технологий в различных отраслях экономики.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая трансформация, искусственный интеллект, цифровая экономика, четвертая, промышленная революция, технологии, экономика, информационные технологии, социальные и экологические аспекты, политика и регулирование, цифровая инфраструктура, глобализация, технология блокчейна, рынок труда и занятость, автоматизация.*

The world is moving into a new phase of disruptive development - it is one of the most discussed topics in boardrooms, directors and parliaments around the world. The Fourth Industrial Revolution: a collective term denoting a whole host of ongoing and upcoming transformations in the familiar systems that surround us. While this may not seem like a big deal to those of us who see small but noticeable changes in our daily routine, it is actually very serious. The Fourth Industrial Revolution, along with the First, Second and Third Industrial Revolutions, opens a new chapter in the development of mankind. As before, it is based on the massive distribution of a number of new technologies.

These advanced technologies build on the achievements of previous industrial revolutions, in particular the digital systems of the Third Industrial Revolution. There are twelve groups of new technologies that we will consider in the second section of the book, including artificial intelligence, robotics, additive manufacturing (3D printing), neurotechnology, biotechnology, virtual and augmented reality, advanced materials and energy technologies.

However, ideas and technologies that we do not yet know about will also play a role.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is not just a name for the changes brought about by technological progress. Above all, it is an opportunity to define a framework for public debate that helps everyone - from politicians and technology leaders to citizens of all countries, from all social groups and at all income levels - understand how powerful, promising, interoperable technologies affect our world. and learn to direct this influence [1].

To do this, we need to change our attitude towards new technologies. They should not be considered irresistible external forces that will inevitably determine our future. But we cannot take the opposite point of view, viewing technology simply as tools that can be used as we please.

We must better understand how new technologies that reflect and embody human values are interconnected and how they influence us when we make decisions about their funding, development, implementation and innovation. Without this, we are unlikely to be able to combine resources and efforts to develop the legal framework and organize collective action to create the future we desire.

There is a need to look at Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies beyond mere tools or unavoidable forces, and look for opportunities to enable more people to positively impact their families, organizations and communities by purposefully impacting the important systems that surround us.

By “systems” we mean the norms, rules, expectations, goals, organizations and incentives that shape our behavior every day, as well as the infrastructure and flows of people and resources necessary for our economic, political and social life. These systems determine how we manage our health, how we make decisions, produce and consume goods and services, how we work, communicate and move, and even how we understand what it means to be human.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution will radically change all these and many other aspects of our lives, just as previous revolutions did.

Industrial revolutions, growth and prospects

Over the past 250 years, three industrial revolutions have occurred. They changed the process of creating value and the world as a whole.

During each of them, technologies, political systems and social institutions evolved. Not only production changed, but also people’s views of themselves, their attitude towards each other and towards the environment.

The First Industrial Revolution began in the British textile industry in the mid-18th century thanks to the mechanization of the spinning and weaving process. Over the next hundred years, mechanization transformed all existing industries and created many new ones - machine tools, steel mills, steam engines, and railroads appeared.

Thanks to the shift in cooperation and competition, a completely new system of creation, exchange and distribution of value has emerged and many sectors of the economy have changed beyond recognition: from agricultural to manufacturing, from communications to transport. The modern meaning of the word “industrial” is not enough to describe the scale of this revolution; the English word industry as understood by the 19th century thinkers Thomas Carlyle is more suitable. Carlyle) and John Stuart Mill (John Stuart Mill), who used it to describe all activities related to human labor.

The First Industrial Revolution led to the spread of colonialism and environmental degradation, but increased human well-being. Before 1750, even in the richest countries - Great Britain, France, Prussia, the Netherlands, as well as in the North American colonies, average economic growth was no more than 0.2% per year, and even this value was unstable. Inequality was much worse than it is now, and average per capita incomes we would consider today to be poverty-stricken. But by 1850, thanks to technology, annual economic growth in the same countries rose to 2-3%, and per capita incomes also grew steadily [2].

Between 1870 and 1930, a new wave of technology continued economic growth and built on the success of the First Industrial Revolution. The radio, telephone, television, home appliances, and electric lighting demonstrated the transformative power of electricity. The internal combustion engine enabled the creation of cars and planes, and subsequently their ecosystems - with new jobs and highway networks. There have also been breakthroughs in chemistry, giving the world new materials, including thermosetting plastics, and new processes. Thus, the Haber - Bosch ammonia synthesis process paved the way for cheap nitrogen fertilizers, the “green revolution” of the 1950s and the subsequent sharp population growth. The Second Industrial Revolution ushered in the modern world, from sanitation to international air travel.

Around 1950, breakthroughs began in information theory and digital computing. These technologies formed the core of the Third Industrial Revolution. As before, the industrial revolution was not driven by technology itself, but by its impact on economic and social systems. The ability to store, process and transmit information digitally has transformed most industries. The labor and social relations of billions of people have changed radically. The combined impact of three industrial revolutions has produced incredible increases in prosperity—at least for those living in developed countries.

About one sixth of the world's population lives in countries that are members of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Today, per capita income in these countries is 30 to 100 times greater than in 1800.

The process of technological innovation - its invention, commercialization, widespread implementation and use - is the strongest factor in increasing wealth and well-being. Today, the average person lives longer, enjoys better health and economic stability, and is far less likely to die a violent death than in any previous era. Since the beginning of the First Industrial Revolution, average real income per capita in OECD countries has increased by 2900%. During the same time, life expectancy has more than doubled in most countries: from 40 years to more than 80 in the UK and from 23.5 to 65 in India.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has a positive impact on many areas. For example, quantum computing offers incredible breakthroughs in the modeling and optimization of complex systems, allowing for much greater efficiency in areas ranging from logistics to drug discovery. Distributed ledger technologies can significantly reduce costs for all parties involved in transactions—for example, when determining the origin of diamonds—and also provide a source of new

value flows represented by digital products and services. Trusted digital identities will make new markets accessible to everyone connected to the Internet. Virtual and mixed reality offer a new way of perceiving the world around us, allowing us to learn faster and put knowledge into practice - anytime, anywhere. New materials could dramatically improve the energy capacity of batteries, expanding the range of applications for civilian and military drones, opening up new power options for vulnerable populations, and accelerating the comprehensive modernization of transportation systems [4].

These benefits may seem entirely dependent on technological progress, but it is unclear when they will be realized and who will be able to benefit from them. In addition to the benefits, the development of the Fourth Industrial Revolution also creates new challenges that could exacerbate inequality, social tensions and political fragmentation, while vulnerable groups are increasingly affected by economic uncertainty and natural disasters. What kind of thinking and what social institutions will we need to create a world where the highest levels of civilization will be available to every person? To shape a fair and inclusive future, we will have to change both mentality and social order. As the experience of previous industrial revolutions shows, to fully realize the benefits of new technologies during the coming restructuring of systems, the world must solve three urgent problems.

The first challenge is to ensure a fair distribution of the benefits of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The wealth and prosperity created by previous revolutions was and remains unevenly distributed. Although inequality between countries has fallen markedly since the 1970s due to the rapid development of states that have transitioned to market economies, inequality within countries is rising. Average annual incomes in developed countries fell by 2.4% between 2011 and 2016, and in 2015 the United States saw its first decline in life expectancy in 25 years, largely due to worsening health among the white working class. People may be unable to take advantage of technology for many reasons: because the technology is unavailable, expensive, or irrelevant, because it is biased, whether overt or implicit, or because organizations seek to capture profits and concentrate wealth [6].

Second task it is necessary to control the negative consequences and risks of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. During previous revolutions, too little was done to protect vulnerable populations, the environment and future generations

from unintended consequences, the costs of progress, spillovers and the deliberate abuse of new opportunities.

The problem of negative and unintended consequences is particularly acute given the power of Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies and the uncertainty of its long-term impacts on complex social and environmental systems.

The greatest concern is the risk of sudden and irreparable damage to the biosphere in the process of geoengineering work, as well as the development of artificial intelligence, the goals of which may not correspond to human ones. Quantum computers will render many cryptographic techniques useless and could pose a serious threat to the privacy and security of users of new computer technologies. The widespread adoption of private driverless vehicles could further congest the roads of densely populated cities, and virtual reality could worsen the problem of online aggression, increasing the psychological damage from it [5].

The third challenge is to ensure that the Fourth Industrial Revolution unfolds in human interests and under human control. It is necessary to respect universal human values as such, and not consider them only from a financial point of view. Moreover, the emphasis on human interests means that humanity's capabilities as a significant force capable of influencing the fate of the world should be expanded, not limited. This task is especially important because the technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution are qualitatively different from all previous ones. As explained in Chapter 12, these technologies can invade what has until now been a private space, our minds. They can predict our thoughts and influence our behavior. They are able to analyze what is happening and make decisions using methods and data that are incomprehensible or too complex for humans. They can change cells in the human body, affecting unborn children. At the same time, digital networks will allow technologies to spread much faster than in the entire previous history of technological progress.

A new way of thinking for leaders

These three challenges—fair distribution of benefits, managing externalities, and guaranteeing a humanistic future—are unlikely to have simple top-down solutions through legislation and well-intentioned government initiatives. Today's combination of international and government institutions, market structures, organized and spontaneous social movements, and incentives is unlikely to result in powerful new technologies becoming widely available, benign, and entirely pro-consumer. The world is still struggling with many problems associated with the previous three industrial revolutions: average wages in developed countries have stagnated or even fallen; Developing countries are

still struggling to translate economic growth into widespread improvements in living standards, yet statistically one in ten lives in extreme poverty. To paraphrase Madeleine Albright (Albright), we try to understand and manage 21st century technologies using 20th century thinking and a set of 19th century government institutions. It is obvious that institutional changes are necessary to solve new problems. It is also necessary to adapt the way of thinking to the challenges of the 21st century [2].

Conclusions

Many transformative technologies are just beginning to emerge from laboratories, garages and research departments around the world, and the laws necessary to regulate them are still being written and finalized. Therefore, right now, active citizens and leaders from all industries have the opportunity to influence the development of systems of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. If we succeed, we can ensure the well-being of the wider population, reduce inequality and restore the trust that, when lacking, creates political tensions and divisions in society. The Fourth Industrial Revolution may produce systems that can make society more prosperous, increase life expectancy, increase levels of economic and physical security, and open up new opportunities for useful and interesting activities in a sustainable ecological environment.

List of references

1. Gulin, K.A. On the role of the Internet of things in the transition to the fourth industrial revolution / K.A. Gulin, V.S. Uskov // Problems of territory development. – 2017. – No. 4. – No. (90). – pp. 112-131.
2. Markeeva, A.V. Internet of things: opportunities and threats for modern organizations / A.V. Markeeva // Society: sociology, psychology, pedagogy. – 2016. – No. 2. – P. 42-46.
3. Yanitsky, O.N. Reflections on the book: Klaus Schwab. The Fourth Industrial Revolution: trans. from English – M.: Publishing house “E”, 2017. – 208 p., with illus. (with a foreword by German Gref) [Electronic resource] / O.N. Yanitsky // Official portal of the IS RAS. – 2017. – URL: <http://www.isras.ru/publ.html?id=4972>
4. "The Fourth Industrial Revolution" by Klaus Schwab
5. "The Future of Work: Robots, AI, and Automation" by Darrell M. West
6. Balatsky, E. V. Global challenges of the fourth industrial revolution / E. V. Balatsky // Terra economicus . – 2019. – T. 17. – No. 2. – P. 6-22. – DOI 10.23683/2073-6606-2019-17-2-6-22.

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